

An Overview of Microfinance Sector in Bosnia and Herzegovina: Is There a Room for Islamic Microfinance?

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Abstract

Bosnia and Herzegovina (B&H) is a transitional country trying to get back on tracks after the aggression of 1990th. Conventional microfinance industry developed reasonably well during the last fifteen years or so. Five microfinance institutions are among the Top 50 in the World. The number of the institutions providing microfinance services has increased enormously since the mid-'90th. The laws are implemented and microfinance sector is under the respective banking rules and regulations. With high unemployment rate, which is in range between 20-40 percent, the microfinance is a very attractive way of financing. Nevertheless, the industry is under a great pressure from the global financial crisis that showed the flaws within the otherwise a perfect example of success story of microfinance practices. Majority of Bosnians are Muslims. As result, there is a dire need of Islamic banking and finance industry to meet the needs of growing Islamic awareness among ordinary people. To date, there is only one Islamic bank in the country, Bosna Bank International (BBI). Unfortunately, since there is no law regulating Islamic banking and finance, even BBI is regulated according to the laws applied to the conventional banks. Implementing and passing the laws with regard to Islamic banking and finance as well as to Islamic microfinancing is not an easy process. It is believed, however, that with the help of other Muslim countries in general and IDB in particular, Islamic microfinancing industry could be a successful story in Bosnia. The paper aims to review the microfinance industry, its legal framework and status, as well as to briefly discuss the need for Islamic microfinance services in B&H.

Keywords: *microfinance, microcredit, Local Initiative Project (LIP), poverty alleviation, Bosnia and Herzegovina*

1. Introduction

More than one quarter of a million people were killed during the aggression on Bosnia & Herzegovina (B&H). A further 1.2 million were internally displaced and

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some 800.000 were forced to flee the country. B&H suffered extensive destruction of housing, severe damage to its infrastructure and economic activities in addition to widespread incidence of murder and rape of civilians. Over 40% of the housing stock was damaged or destroyed, and the habitable homes left behind by displaced persons and refugees were in most instances occupied by other displaced persons in search of shelter.

Microcredit¹ sector of Bosnia and Herzegovina played a crucial role in reducing the poverty and supporting of the development of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) by providing the financial assistance to the people that otherwise could not get the financing through the conventional banks. Through the Local Initiative Projects (LIP I and LIP II),² that were supported by World Bank and other international NGOs, the microfinance technique entered the B&H market.

Due to the wonderful results achieved over the last twelve years, B&H is placed among the top countries when it comes to the development of microfinance sector. In many cases the microfinance institutions (MFIs) are considered to be similar to the conventional banks. However, the conventional banks issue credits to rich clients who have a credit history and who can provide collateral, while on the other side MFIs serve the clients without collateral and with low-income. Since 1996, some 12-14 MFIs have been operating in B&H.³ In 2007, eleven of them, which are members of Association of Microfinance Institutions of Bosnia and Herzegovina, covered 97% of microfinance market in B&H with over 400 million “*konvertibilna marka*” (KM or convertible mark, international currency code is BAM)⁴ issued.

Nevertheless, MFIs are faced with a problem of rising bad loans and for the first time in their history they are faces with shrinking growth rates. Consequently, the

¹ Words microcredit and microfinance are used interchangeably throughout this paper.

² Hartarska, V. & Nadolnyak, D. 2007. 'An Impact Analysis of Microfinance in Bosnia and Herzegovina ', [online at <http://ssrn.com/abstract=1105052>], Dunn, E. 2005. 'Impacts of Microcredit on Clients in Bosnia and Herzegovina.' Foundation for Sustainable Development of the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina and Republika Srpska Development and Employment Foundation, Kuehnast, K. March, 2001. 'Innovative Approaches to Microfinance in Post-Conflict Situations: Bosnia Local Initiatives Project.' Social Development Notes, Note No. 50.

³ This is according to the Association of Microfinance Institutions in Bosnia and Herzegovina. See: www.amfi.ba However, some say that the number is much higher. See: Živko (2006).

⁴ KM is short form for “*konvertibilna marka*” (convertible mark or BAM) - the national currency introduced in 1998. The exchange rate, pegged to EURO, is: 1 EURO = 1.955830 KM. For details visit the Central Bank’s website at www.cbbh.ba.

predictions about the future growth are more conservative with MFIs trying to handle the first real shock of the sector.

The aim of this paper is to review the existing written materials on the microfinance sector in Bosnia and Herzegovina and to make general assessment. Due to limited access to the relevant data, this paper will focus more on theoretical and descriptive analysis. Nevertheless, it will be beneficial to the future researchers on the topic by providing comprehensive overlook of the microfinance sector and market in B&H. Finally, the paper aims at highlighting the possibilities and challenges for implementing Islamic microfinance scheme in the country.

The paper consists of five parts including the introduction. The second part provides an overall review of B&H, where the main economic indicators and financial market structure are detailed. The third part is dealing with microfinance sector in B&H and conventional MFIs. This part covers literature review, an overview of microfinance sector, its legal framework, an impact of MFIs on B&H as well as its sourcing. Furthermore, it briefly highlights the current challenges and way forward for MFIs. Part five is dealing with the possibilities and challenges for the implementation of Islamic microfinance in B&H. Finally, the part six is left for concluding remarks.

2. Bosnia and Herzegovina: An Overview

Bosnia and Herzegovina is a transitional country consisting of two entities: Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina (FB&H) and Republika Srpska (RS), with District Brčko as a *de facto* third entity. The Federation is further divided into 10 cantons. This division is a direct result of the constitution made in Dayton, Ohio when the Dayton Peace Accords were signed in 1995. This peace agreement ended the aggression on Bosnia and Herzegovina by Bosnian Serbs - supported by neighboring Serbia and Montenegro.

Bosnia and Herzegovina is among the poorest states among the ex-Yugoslav federation. The aggression on B&H had enormous effects on Bosnian economy that almost stopped its productions from 1992 to 1995 causing unemployment rate to soar. The *konvertibilna marka* (convertible mark or BAM) - the national currency introduced in 1998 – was pegged to the German mark and now to the EURO, boosting the confidence in the currency and the banking sector. As transitional country, B&H is undergoing the privatization, a process that has been slow, painful and in many cases unsuccessful. Banking reforms accelerated in 2001 with foreign banks, primarily from Western Europe, now controlling majority of the banking sector. The main macroeconomic problems include a sizeable current account deficit and high unemployment rate, among others (See Table: 1).

Table 1: Major economic indicators in Bosnia and Herzegovina

Indicator	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008
<i>GDP* (in KM)</i>	11,599	12,829	14,505	15,786	16,928	19,121	21,647	25,100
<i>GDP pe capita (in KM)</i>	3,054	3,611	3,785	4,109	4,405	4,976	5,634	6,531
<i>GDP* (in USD)</i>	5,307	6,655	8,367	10,020	10,763	12,262	15,143	18,779
<i>GDP pe capita (in USD)</i>	1,397	1,738	2,184	2,608	2,801	3,191	3,941	4,886
<i>Real GDP (growth rate in %)</i>	4.5%	4.9%	3.8%	6.3%	3.9%	6.9%	6.0%	5.5%
<i>Inflation[#]</i>	3.1%	0.4%	0.6%	0.4%	3.9%	6.1%	1.5%	7.4%
<i>Unemployment</i>	40.9%	40.9%	42%	43.2%	N.A.	31.1%	29%	23.4%
<i>Current account balance (in mil. KM)</i>	-1,630	-2,449	-2,814	-2,579	-2,934	-1,505	-2,253	-3,675
<i>Current account balance (in mil. USD)</i>	-744	-1,192	-1,630	-1,639	-1,846	-981	-1,595	-2,851
<i>Current account balance (in % of GDP)</i>	-14.1%	-17.7%	-19.4%	-16.3%	-17.3%	-7.9%	-10.4%	-14.6%
<i>Population (in thousands)</i>	3,798	3,828	3,832	3,842	3,843	3,843	3,842	3,843
<i>Annual average exchange rate KM/USD</i>	2.1	2.0768	1.7335	1.5755	1.5728	1.5594	1.4295	1.3366

Source: Central Bank of Bosnia and Herzegovina and B&H Agency for statistics.⁵ Real GDP is estimate of B&H Central Bank, besides growth rate of Real GDP for 2004, 2005, 2006 and 2007 which are produced by B&H Agency for statistics.

Note: * Nominal GDP in billions

[#] Since 2005, inflation has been monitored on the basis of the index of consumer prices, and not on the basis of the retail price index, as was the case previously. Namely, in September 2007 the B&H Statistics Agency published the data on the movement of the consumer price index (CPI) from January 2005. This index, as a measure of inflation, is fully aligned with international standards.

Table 2: Structure of financial system in Bosnia and Herzegovina

Number of	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008
<i>Banks</i>	33	33	32	32	30
<i>Pension fund</i>	2	2	2	2	2
<i>Insurance company</i>	29	26	25	25	27

⁵ Central Bank of Bosnia and Herzegovina, Annual Reports, (Various Issues). For details visit: <http://www.cbbh.ba>. See also: Agency for statistics of Bosnia and Herzegovina, <http://www.bhas.ba>.

<i>Privatisation investment fund</i>	24	24	24	26	25
<i>Microcredit organization*</i>	46	50	50	50	26

Source: Central Bank Bosnia and Herzegovina.⁶

Note: 12 microcredit organizations cover 98% of market

It is due to the country's devastation of the 1990s aggression that micro-credit sector developed into a cornerstone of the recovery. This micro-credit sector has grown tremendously since its introduction and has been praised for its success in reviving the small businesses.⁷ Financial intermediation of the micro financial sector comprises around 4% of the financial sector in BH. In line with the legislation in force, monitoring over micro credit organizations is entrusted to the Entities' Banking Agencies and as of 2008 there are 26 organizations (19 in FBH and 7 in RS).⁸ In the following section we will try to elaborate its development.

3.0 Microfinance Institutions (Mfis) In B&H

3.1 Literature Review

The first microfinance project in Bosnia and Herzegovina started in 1996 in Tuzla. This project helped other MFIs develop better lending practices and organizational structure. According to Goronja, the lending practices had to be adjusted and culturally appropriate if institutions is to work successfully.⁹ Her study covered the early development of microfinance industry in B&H.

There were several studies on the impact of microfinance in Bosnia. First two, by Matul and Tsilikounas¹⁰ and Dunn,¹¹ mainly studied the impact of a single MFI,

⁶ Central Bank of Bosnia and Herzegovina, Annual Reports, (Various Issues). For details visit: <http://www.cbbh.ba>.

⁷ Cain, P. January 4, 2010. 'Microfinance meltdown in Bosnia', *Al Jazeera.Net*, [online at <http://english.aljazeera.net/focus/2010/01/20101393659573655.html>], Zuvella, M. 2009. 'Bosnia's banks must tackle bad loan rise.' *Reuters*. Sarajevo: Reuters, Niksic, S. July 5, 2009. 'Recession could boost Bosnia micro-credit sector.' *Business Week*.

⁸ CBBH 2009. 'CBBH Annual Report 2008.' Sarajevo: Central Bank of Bosnia and Herzegovina.

⁹ Goronja, N. 1999. "'The Evolution of Microfinance in a Successful Post-Conflict Transition: The Case Study for Bosnia-Herzegovina".' *ILO/UNHCR Workshop: Microfinance in Post Conflict Countries*. Geneva.

¹⁰ Matul, M. & Tsilikounas, C. 2004. 'Role of microfinance in the household reconstruction process in Bosnia & Herzegovina', *Journal of international development*, 16, [online at http://www.banyanglobal.com/pdf/micro_2004.01_bos-hrz.pdf].

while the third one by Hartarska and Nadolnyak¹² focused on the impact of all microfinance institutions operating in B&H. Matul and Tsilikounas¹³ within Imp-Act project¹⁴ studied the role of micro-enterprise lending in the household reconstruction process during 1996-2002 in B&H. This research examined the impact of microcredit on reconstruction. The first study showed evidence that this program led to an increase in income, number of workers, and investment. However, this study showed that these indicators were relatively better among clients with longer use of credit and with a stronger enterprise to start with.

Dunn¹⁵ studied the impact on client income in MFIs supported by the LIP. Her study was designed to address four key questions:

- i. Do microcredit organizations in B&H reach their target populations?
- ii. Does microcredit improve the household welfare of borrowers?
- iii. Does microcredit promote business development?
- iv. Does microcredit ease or speed the post-conflict transition?

In order to answer these questions, her evaluation relied on combination of a longitudinal survey and case study interviews. She collected data by interviewing about 3,000 clients and comparable non-clients in 2002 and re-interviewing most of them again in 2004. From the regression analysis she concluded that the clients' income increased from participation. The study also showed that microfinance programs increased employment and wages of non-household employees.

¹¹ Dunn, E. 2005. 'Impacts of Microcredit on Clients in Bosnia and Herzegovina.' Foundation for Sustainable Development of the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina and Republika Srpska Development and Employment Foundation.

¹² Hartarska, V. & Nadolnyak, D. 2007. 'An Impact Analysis of Microfinance in Bosnia and Herzegovina', [online at <http://ssrn.com/abstract=1105052>].

¹³ Matul, M. & Tsilikounas, C. 2004. 'Role of microfinance in the household reconstruction process in Bosnia & Herzegovina', *Journal of international development*, 16, [online at http://www.banyanglobal.com/pdf/micro_2004.01_bos-hrz.pdf].

¹⁴ ImpAct Programme – www.imp-act.org - is a collaboration which brings together 29 MFOs in 20 countries, a team of academics from three UK universities, international NGOs, policy-makers and donors. MFC acts as regional coordinator and TA provider to 7 regional MFIs participating in the Programme.

¹⁵ Dunn, E. 2005. 'Impacts of Microcredit on Clients in Bosnia and Herzegovina.' Foundation for Sustainable Development of the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina and Republika Srpska Development and Employment Foundation.

Hartarska and Nadolnyak¹⁶ studied the impact of microfinance by applying the financing constraint approach. According to this approach, improvement in access to credit, resulting from availability of microfinance, is reflected in the sensitivity of microbusinesses' investment to availability of internal funds. It used data collected from the Living Standards Measurement Survey of the World Bank, the Local Initiative Project and the Association of Bosnian Microfinance Institutions. This study shows that MFIs improved access to credit in municipalities where two or more MFIs offered financial products because the investment in local microenterprises was less sensitive to availability of internal funds than was investment in municipalities where microfinancing was limited or non-existent and where microentrepreneurs had to rely more on internal funds for investment.¹⁷

Zivko, in his papers, evaluated the microfinance sector in B&H. He evaluated the legal frameworks and indicated the problems faced with MFIs. He also highlighted the necessary changes that need to be implemented in new Law to facilitate the development of microfinance industry in B&H.¹⁸

By 2001, according to Berryman and Pytkowska,¹⁹ microfinance institutions disbursed over 20,000 microcredits. In the same year, the average MFI had 9 branches and covered about 22 municipalities. Their research focused on data from six institutions: EKI-World Vision, Mi-Bospo, Mikrofin, Partner, Prizma, and Sunrise; all of which participated in the 10th edition of the MicroBanking Bulletin²⁰

¹⁶ Hartarska, V. & Nadolnyak, D. 2007. 'An Impact Analysis of Microfinance in Bosnia and Herzegovina', [online at <http://ssrn.com/abstract=1105052>].

¹⁷ Ibid.

¹⁸ Zivko, I. 2006. 'Role of Microcredit Organization in Financial System Transitional Countries – A Case of Bosnia and Herzegovina.' *3rd International Conference An Enterprise Odyssey: Integration or Disintegration*, Zagreb: University of Zagreb, Faculty of Economics and Business. Zagreb: University of Zagreb, Faculty of Economics and Business, Živko, I. 2006. 'Mikrokreditne organizacije u Bosni i Hercegovini.' *Financijski propis i praksa*, 12:7, Živko, I. 2007. 'Mikrokreditni sektor Bosne i Hercegovine u funkciji ekonomskog razvoja – iskustva i izazovi.' *Zbornik radova, II. Međunarodni simpozij "Financije i računovodstvo u funkciji gospodarskog rasta Bosne i Hercegovine"*: 113-27. Mostar.

¹⁹ Berryman, M. & Pytkowska, J. 2003. "'A review of the Bosnian microfinance sector: move to financial self-sufficiency'", *Microfinance Centre for Central and Eastern Europe and the New Independent States*, [online at <http://www.mfc.org.pl>].

²⁰ The MicroBanking Bulletin (MBB) has become the premier benchmarking source for the microfinance industry. Originally an output of the MicroBanking Standards Project, the MBB is now one of the principal products offered by the MIX (Microfinance Information eXchange). For more details see: Berryman and Pytkowska (2003).

and have provided over four years of financial and institutional data. By 2003, these six institutions covered by this research had around 40,000 active borrowers, 61% of whom were women. This number of active borrowers represented 62% of the clients served by the 40 largest MFIs operating in B&H.

3.2. Microfinance Sector – Historical Overview

According to Hartarska and Nadolnyak,²¹ during '90s, the international community supported about 70 projects related to microfinance. Back in 1996, the World Bank initiated the Local Initiatives (Microfinance) Project (LIP) in order to support the post-conflict reconstruction and economic recovery of Bosnia and Herzegovina. The main goal of LIP I was “to promote economic opportunities for the war-affected population and economically poor citizens of B&H.”²² They believed that self-employment as well as micro and small businesses are important means for creating jobs and bringing about prosperity. The first Local Initiatives Project (LIP I) began in 1996 to June 30, 2000. It was financed by the World Bank and a number of other bilateral and multilateral donors at the total cost of USD 21.8 million.

Table 3: Financing of LIP I	
Source	USD
World Bank	6,694,208
Italy	3,223,262
Holland	4,590,000
Switzerland	1,123,170
Austria	584,857
Japan	2,000,000
UNHCR	3,538,003
UNDP	51,000
TOTAL	21,804,500
Source: Dunn (2005)	

The main objectives of the Local Initiative Project I were as follows:

²¹ Hartarska, V. & Nadolnyak, D. 2007. 'An Impact Analysis of Microfinance in Bosnia and Herzegovina', [online at <http://ssrn.com/abstract=1105052>].

²² Dunn, E. 2005. 'Impacts of Microcredit on Clients in Bosnia and Herzegovina.' Foundation for Sustainable Development of the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina and Republika Srpska Development and Employment Foundation.

- (i) to provide access to credit to the economically-disadvantaged and war-affected, specifically low-income micro-entrepreneurs who have no access to credit from the commercial banking sector;
- (ii) to facilitate the development of independent, financially viable microfinance institutions that will continue to provide credit to low income entrepreneurs over the long-term;
- (iii) to create an appropriate legal and regulatory environment for the provision of credit and savings services to low income entrepreneurs.²³

This project was highly satisfactory. Five years after the start of the program, as of March 31, 2001, some 80,000 loans have been disbursed to microentrepreneurs throughout the country. As result some 100,000 jobs have been created or sustained. Repayment rate was very high at 98.5%, with only 1.21% of outstanding repayments (30 days past due). In overall, the living conditions improved during this period and 79% of borrowers stated that the loan had significantly improved their economic situation.²⁴

As result of great performance of the first LIP, the World Bank Board of Directors approved in July 2001 an IDA credit of US\$ 20 million to finance a second LIP in Bosnia and Herzegovina (LIP II). The counterpart entity government financed US\$ 4.06 million, and the total value of LIP II was US\$ 24.06 million. Its aims were to address the urgent need to raise incomes, develop businesses and create jobs in B&H through providing credit and other financial services to people with low-income. According to Dunn, LIP II had two specific objectives:²⁵

- a) Financing the growth and institutional development of high-performing microfinance institutions that have the capacity to serve a significant number of low-income clients who do not have, or have limited access to, commercial bank sources; and
- b) Supporting the transition of the microfinance sector towards sustainable sources of financing.

Project LIP II was highly successful as can be seen from the Table below:

²³ Ibid. "Local Initiative Project is evaluated as highly satisfactory in helping people earn their living in Bosnia and Herzegovina". (2001). Retrieved from <http://www.seerecon.org/news/n20010627a.htm>

²⁴ An independent Client Survey commissioned by the Local Initiative Departments (the monitoring agencies of the project) carried out in 1999.

²⁵ Dunn, E. 2005. 'Impacts of Microcredit on Clients in Bosnia and Herzegovina.' Foundation for Sustainable Development of the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina and Republika Srpska Development and Employment Foundation.

Table 4: Achievements of LIP II		
<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Planned</i>	<i>Achieved June 30, 2005</i>
Number of loans disbursed	150,000	380,051
Amount of loans disbursed in KM	430,000,000	1,239,887,970
Number of active clients	50,000	98,852
Gross portfolio outstanding in KM	125,000,000	230,438,638
Portfolio at risk (over 30 days)	< 5%	0.99%

Source: *The World Bank*, Report No: 34234-BA

At the end of 2007, the *Forbes* magazine conducted a study and published the first-ever list of the World's Top 50 Microfinance Institutions. Among these Top 50 microfinance institutions five of them were from Bosnia. These microfinance institutions are: EKI, Partner, MICROFIN Banja Luka, MI-BOSPO Tuzla, and Microcredit Organization Sunrise. They were placed 14th, 18th, 24th, 32nd and 39th respectively.²⁶ This proves once again that MFIs in B&H are the true representatives of the successful microfinance practices. By the end of 2008, there were some 390,000 outstanding loans, amounting to over KM 1 billion (\$723 million).²⁷

3.3. Legal Framework

Initially microcredit organizations were registered as non-deposit taking, non-profit, non-governmental organizations. According to the new, harmonized Laws on Microcredit Organizations there are basically two forms of MFIs, namely: *microcredit foundations*, as a non-profit form (with their social role and society benefit emphasized) and *microcredit companies*, as a for-profit form that can be formed as a limited liability or joint stock companies.

²⁶ Swibel, M. n.d. "The 50 Top Microfinance Institutions", *Forbes.com*, [online at http://www.forbes.com/2007/12/20/microfinance-philanthropy-credit-biz-cz_ms_1220microfinance_table.html]. Forbes' first-ever list of the World's Top 50 Microfinance Institutions were chosen from a field of 641 micro-credit providers. The list was prepared by the Microfinance Information Exchange (www.themix.org) under the direction of Forbes magazine. To qualify, the institutions must have made available their audited financial statements and must have passed review by a Forbes panel of advisers. This sortable list gives the rank (out of 641) for the top institutions according to scale, which is based on the size of their gross loan portfolio; efficiency, which considers operating expense and the cost per borrower as a percent of the gross national income per capita of their country of operation; risk, which looks at the quality of their loan portfolios, measured as the percent of the portfolio at risk greater than 30 days; and return, which is measured as a combination of return on equity and return on assets. Each category is equally weighted for an institution's overall ranking. For more details see: Swibel (n.d.)

²⁷ Cain, P. January 4, 2010. 'Microfinance meltdown in Bosnia', *Al Jazeera.Net*, [online at <http://english.aljazeera.net/focus/2010/01/20101393659573655.html>].

Prior to 2006, the federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina (FB&H) and Republic of Srpska (RS) had separate laws and regulations governing the establishment, registration and operation of microcredit organizations. For FB&H it was Law on Microcredit Organizations from 2000, while for RS it was Law on Microcredit Organizations from 2001. Although these laws made it possible for MCOs to develop into a respectable financial sector, the lack of harmony between these two regulatory regimes caused problems for very active and ever-growing MCOs in practice.²⁸ Due to these and similar irregularities, as well as to the aspirations of the MCOs to develop further and to compete for the B&H market, the laws were amended and harmonized at the State level. The current, harmonized law that is implemented for MFIs is Law on Microcredit Organizations.²⁹

According to this Law, the microcredit organizations are non-depository financial organizations whose core activity is provision of microcredits. A microcredit organization carries out the microcredit activity in compliance with this law, with the objective of improving the financial position of microcredit beneficiaries, increasing employment, providing the support to the development of entrepreneurship and acquisition of profits.

As such, it is a legal entity which may be founded and may operate as a microcredit company or as a microcredit foundation. In order for a microcredit organization to become a microcredit company it has to be registered in the court registry of business companies in compliance with this law and the Law on Registration of Business Companies in the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina ("Official Gazette of Federation B&H", No:27/05 and 68/05). The status of a legal entity is acquired by a microcredit foundation with the entry into the registry of foundations in compliance with this law and the Law on Associations and Foundations of the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina ("Official Gazette of the Federation B&H", No: 45/02). To start its operations a microcredit company/foundation has to acquire the permit from the Banking Agency of the Federation of B&H.

A microcredit organization may be established by at least 3 domestic or foreign persons and by at least 1 domestic or foreign legal entity, under the conditions stipulated by this Law. A person being authorized for the representation of the microcredit organization submits to the Banking Agency an application for the issuance of the permit, together with all prescribed documents and evidence of fulfilling the conditions stipulated by this Law. The Agency issues a decision on approving or refusing the application within 60 days from the date of receiving an application.

²⁸ Lyman, T. R. 2006, January. 'Legal and Regulatory Environment for Microfinance in Bosnia and Herzegovina: A Decade of Evolution and Prognosis for the Future. ' *Policy Monitor*: 1-3. Maryland: Microfinance Centre for Central and Eastern Europe and the New Independent States.

²⁹ 'Law on Microcredit Organizations "Official Gazette of the Federation of B&H", No. 59/06.', 'Law on Microcredit Organizations "Official Herald of Republic of Srpska", No. 64/06.'

The newly harmonized Law allowed to the MCOs with their headquarters in FB&H to operate in RS, and vice versa, through the opening of new branches and by getting necessary permits required by that entity and in accordance to this Law. The main activities of MCOs in B&H are as follows:

1. provision of the microcredits
2. some other activities that are in line with microcredit business, such as:
 - i. receiving and giving out gifts and donations and the raising of financial assets and other forms of property from any legal source;
 - ii. giving and pledging/mortgaging property, including microcredits, to secure borrowing; &
 - iii. credit consultations, business counseling and technical assistance aimed at the improvement of credit activities of the microcredit organization and business activities of microcredit beneficiaries.

However, a microcredit organization cannot accept cash deposits and savings deposits from natural persons or legal entities.³⁰

3.4. Impact of Microcredit on Clients in Bosnia and Herzegovina

According to Hartarska and Nadolnyak, Bosnia and Herzegovina has the most dynamic microfinance sector.³¹ Furthermore, they say that the analysis of both its success and setbacks could help microfinance donors and policy makers in other countries to develop and promote microfinance.³² In this section we will try to summarize the key findings of the three-year (2002-2005) impact assessment on clients in B&H that has been conducted under the Local Initiatives (Microfinance) Project II – LIP II.³³

Table-5: Legal framework of microcredit organizations in Bosnia and Herzegovina

Criteria	Federation of Bosnia and	Republic of Srpska	Newly harmonized laws
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³⁰ 'Law on Microcredit Organizations "Official Gazette of the Federation of B&H", No. 24/00.', 'Law on Microcredit Organizations "Official Gazette of the Federation of B&H", No. 59/06.', 'Law on Microcredit Organizations "Official Herald of Republic of Srpska", No. 19/01.', 'Law on Microcredit Organizations "Official Herald of Republic of Srpska", No. 64/06.'

³¹ Hartarska, V. & Nadolnyak, D. 2007. 'An Impact Analysis of Microfinance in Bosnia and Herzegovina ', [online at <http://ssrn.com/abstract=1105052>].

³² Dunn, E. 2005. 'Impacts of Microcredit on Clients in Bosnia and Herzegovina.' Foundation for Sustainable Development of the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina and Republika Srpska Development and Employment Foundation.

³³ Ibid.

	Herzegovina		
Laws and regulations governing registration	Law on Microcredit Organizations (2000)	Law on Microcredit Organizations (2001)	Law on Microcredit Organizations (2006)
Agency for registration	Ministry of Social Policy, Displaced Persons and Refugees	Ministry of Finance	The Banking Agency of the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina & The Banking Agency of Republic of Srpska
Capital requirement	No requirements	€ 2.564 (5.000 BAM)	For company: KM 500,000/ € 255,324 For foundation: KM 50,000/ € 25,532
Reporting and Supervision	No onsite supervision	Occasional onsite supervision	The Banking Agency of FB&H The Banking Agency of RS
Restricted operations	Taking cash and/or saving deposits; profits must be used for microcrediting	Taking cash and/or saving deposits; profits must be used for microcrediting	Taking cash and/or saving deposits
Max. amount of credit	KM 30,000 / € 15,319	KM 30,000 / € 15,319	For company: KM 50,000 / € 25,532 For foundation: KM 10,000 / € 5,106

Source:

Law on Microcredit Organizations "Official Gazette of the Federation of B&H", No. 24/00,

Law on Microcredit Organizations "Official Herald of Republic of Srpska", No. 19/01,

Law on Microcredit Organizations "Official Gazette of the Federation of B&H", No. 59/06,

Law on Microcredit Organizations "Official Herald of Republic of Srpska", No. 64/0

These findings are as follows:

- i. Microcredit increases investment, productivity and incomes

The direct and the most important impact of microcredit on clients in B&H is that microcredit helps the B&H citizens to improve their household welfare, develop their business and contribute to the national growth and development. The study shows that micro-business on average employs 2,15 workers. It also shows that microcredit encourages business investment. As the investments grow, the productivity grows as well bringing about the welfare to the entrepreneurs and their families.

ii. Microcredit strengthens the formal economy

Newly established micro-businesses participate in the formal economy by registering their businesses. This benefits the national economy by improving the tax base and creating a level playing field for business growth and development. According to the study, registered businesses had higher levels of both employment and investment.

iii. Microcredit assists displaced entrepreneurs

Due to the aggression on B&H many residents were forced to flee their homes and refugees are still all over the country (and abroad). Microcredit industry tried to reach to these affected populations. However, the study shows that these people continue to struggle and need special assistance to reintegrate into the national economy.

3.5. Sources of financing of MFIs in Bosnia and Herzegovina

As the financial sector started to develop since 2000, with many foreign banks coming to B&H and introduction of the Laws on MCOs, the microfinancial sector developed as well. Some strong banks, led by Raiffeisen, recognizing the MCOs as their partners and not rivals, began lending to MCOs. This was permitted under the MCO law in both entities. Besides this new source of capital, many MCOs also received as good or even better deals from foreign social investment sources, NGOs etc.³⁴

MFIs in Bosnia and Herzegovina are mainly financed through one of the following three:³⁵

1. subsidized loans - 46,31%
2. commercial loans - 20,84%
3. own sources – 32,85%

The following financial institutions and NGOs are the main contributors to subsidized loans category:

- Foundation for Sustainable Development – LIP II – 14.62%
- Republica Srpska Development and Employment Foundation – LIP II – 7.70%

³⁴ Ibid.

³⁵ Zivko, I. 2006. 'Role of Microcredit Organization in Financial System Transitional Countries– A Case of Bosnia and Herzegovina.' *3rd International Conference An Enterprise Odyssey: Integration or Disintegration, Zagreb: University of Zagreb, Faculty of Economics and Business*. Zagreb: University of Zagreb, Faculty of Economics and Business.

- International NGO “World Vision” – 6.81%
- Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau – KfW – EU Fund – 5.89%
- USAID LAMP – Linking Agricultural Markets for Producers – 3.74%
- USAID BF – Business Finance – 1.54% and etc.³⁶

3.6.A Way Forward

The current global financial crisis put an extra pressure on already difficult conditions of the B&H citizens. The micro-credit sector registered a steady default rate of less than 1.0 percent since 1996, but it is being badly affected by the crisis. Some microfinance institutions reported a rise of portfolio at risk, the trend that started at the end of 2008. Apart from that, the crisis also revealed a more serious problem, growing of the sector too much and too fast. As result, the MFIs started imprudent lending by encouraging the clients to borrow more than they should. The result was that these loans were spent for consumer goods and not business purposes.³⁷

In December 2008, Kemal Kozaric, the governor of Central Bank, reported the rise of non-performing loans of commercial banks as well as the micro-credit sector. In recent years, some of the MFIs witnessed the growth rate between 40-50 percent, but the sector slipped 4 percent for the first time in the first half of 2009. As result, MFIs are now requested to report on their clients to the central bank, the practice that has not been there several months ago.³⁸

The profit motive, as pointed out by Phil Cain, was one of the factors that shifted the focus of the micro-credit sector away from the development. With the new legal framework, MFIs were able to “turn themselves from philanthropic ventures into commercial ones” seeking a pure profit and forgetting their missions.³⁹

A lack of regulation and supervision, combined with the easy credit schemes fuelled the bubble that had to burst one day. The way things have been handled by the lenders, last

³⁶ Ibid.

³⁷ Cain, P. January 4, 2010. 'Microfinance meltdown in Bosnia', *Al Jazeera.Net*, [online at <http://english.aljazeera.net/focus/2010/01/20101393659573655.html>], Niksic, S. July 5, 2009. 'Recession could boost Bosnia micro-credit sector.' *Business Week*.

³⁸ Zuvela, M. 2009. 'Bosnia's banks must tackle bad loan rise.' *Reuters*. Sarajevo: Reuters.

³⁹ Cain, P. January 4, 2010. 'Microfinance meltdown in Bosnia', *Al Jazeera.Net*, [online at <http://english.aljazeera.net/focus/2010/01/20101393659573655.html>].

couple of years, was not sustainable. It is for these reasons that MFIs in B&H are becoming more conservative in their projections of the future growth and the way things are done. People of B&H, too, are aware of these issues and are more cautious when it comes whether or not to take a loan.⁴⁰ In short, the foundations of MFIs have been shaken for the first time since '90s, and the future of the sector is at stake.

4. Is There A Room For Islamic Microfinance?

Although the conventional microfinance has done a great job in B&H and its infrastructure is well developed, as of now, there is no any MFI that is offering microfinancing based on Islamic principles of finance. However, there have been attempts to provide Islamic microcredits by some Islamic charity organizations (such as Muslim Aid, Muslim Relief, etc), but without much results.

When it comes to the banking sector, the situation is slightly better as there is one Islamic bank. The only Islamic bank in B&H is Bosna Bank International (BBI). BBI⁴¹ was established on October 19, 2000 as the first bank in B&H whose operations are based on the principles of Shari'ah. The share capital of BBI amounted to KM 47.52 million, which at that time, was the largest paid in capital compared to other banks in the country. With that capital, BBI was ready to embark on the reconstruction and further development of Bosnia and Herzegovina.

On March 13, 2002, Bosna Bank International obtained the permit for domestic payment transactions from the Banking Agency of the Federation of B&H and in November the same year the license for deposit insurance. However, there is no law related to Islamic banking and finance. As such, BBI operates under the Banking Law that is guided by conventional rules and regulations.

The current situation is due to several reasons. First, the non-existence of Islamic banking and finance rules and regulations. Second reason may be relatively high capital requirements for establishment of MFI. Third, it is also due to unwillingness (ignorance) of many Muslims of the potential needs for such finance. Finally, in our view, as B&H is the only Muslim majority country in the Europe, there is a reasonable Islamophobia towards anything that has prefix "Islamic."

⁴⁰ Ibid.

⁴¹ The information about BBI is taken from their website directly. For more details visit their website <http://www.bbi.ba/>.

Consequently, the challenges before us are manifold ranging from legal matters, to financial and human capital, as there are a very small number of the people who are having knowledge of Islamic banking and finance practices. Having this in mind, there is a dire need for education of our young citizens through scholarships, fellow programs or internships so that they may get the knowledge of Islamic banking and finance and help us develop this industry in B&H even better. Furthermore, we have to utilize all the media in the process of breaking the ice around the citizens of B&H when it comes to “Islamic” matters. By doing so (i.e. using all available media: TV, radio, newspapers, magazines, internet, etc.) we would accustom people, and even the politicians, to the Islamic financial terminology and this would help us in passing the law related to Islamic banking and finance.

It is our collective duty to help Muslims all over the world. In case of B&H, the OIC countries together with the Islamic Development Bank (IDB) should play a more important role in helping Bosnian Muslims to overcome their financial threats and help them by providing them with alternative. IDB, with all its resources and experience, may help in the process of drafting the law on Islamic banking and finance together with Islamic community in B&H.

Our proposal is for Islamic financial institutions, such as IDB, to finance the establishment of Islamic MFI in B&H. They initiated the establishment of BBI bank and this bank could facilitate the establishment and operations of Islamic MFIs in the future as well. Furthermore, it could enter into an agreement with one of the MFIs currently operating in B&H and offer them financing for implementation of Islamic microfinance services.

5. Conclusion

Over the years, since the Dayton Peace Agreement, the microfinance industry developed rapidly and its key players are among the top MFIs in the World that proves the professional standards of the local MFIs. The studies have showed that microfinancing is having positive impact on household income, investment and development of economy in general.

Unfortunately, the profit motive stoked MFIs to shift their focus from development to profit-making which led to extensive and imprudent lending by the profit-seeking lenders. This practice, combined with global financial crisis, revealed the problems within the sector and relevant parties are worried over the future prospects of MFIs in B&H. We hope that, with the availability of data, the

proper study could be carried out in order to find the real potentials as well as problems of the MFIs.

Finally, the paper revealed that there is no Islamic microfinance institution in B&H. Hence, Bosnian Muslims, having no alternative, are somehow forced to utilize the existing MFIs which are operating in conventional ways. Having this in mind and all the experience of the existing MFIs in B&H, Islamic financial institutions such as IDB should either finance the establishment of an Islamic MFI (as it has financed the establishment of BBI bank) or enter into an agreement with one of the existing MFI which is willing to open some kind of “Islamic window” for Islamic microfinance operations.

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Appendix 1: Members of Association of Microfinance Institutions in B&H

No.	Microcredit org. & address	Tel, fax & e-mail	Director
1	EKI Zvornička 9 71 000 Sarajevo	033/ 651-112; 651-113; 714-200 wvimikro@B&H.net http://www.worldvision.ba/	Sadina Bina
2	LOK micro Skenderija 13 71 000 Sarajevo	033/ 442-931; 442-932; 442-933 central.office@lok.ba info@lok.ba http://www.lok.ba	Nusret Čaušević
3	MI-BOSPO Mirze Delibašića 5 75 000 Tuzla	035/ 252-448; 270-283 bospo@B&H.net http://www.mi-bospo.org/	Nejira Nalić
4	M IKRA Marka Marulića 2/VI Poslovna zgrada «UNIPROMET» 71 000 Sarajevo	033/ 616-162; 714-140; 717-141 fax mikra@mikra.ba http://www.mikra.ba	Sanin Čampara
5	MIKRO ALDI Panorama bb 73 000 Gorazde	038/ 226-456; 222-092; 221-004 mka.aldi@B&H.net http://www.mikroaldi.org/	Ferida Softić
6	MIKROFIN Save Kovačevića 23 78 000 Banja Luka	051/ 301-535 mfbl@inecco.net http://www.mikrofin.com/	Aleksandar Kremenović
7	PARTNER MIKROKREDITNA ORGANIZACIJA Ulica 15 Maja (Trzni centar Sjenjak) 75 000 Tuzla	035/ 245-780; 245-781; 245-782 partner@partner.ba http://www.partner.ba/	Senad Sinanović
8	PRIZMA Kulovića 5/1 71 000 Sarajevo	033/ 552-000; 552-001; 552-002; 209-179 fax hq@prizma.ba http://www.prizma.ba/	Kenan Crnkić
9	SINERGIJA plus Mladena Stojanovića 111 78 000 Banja Luka	051/ 332-600; 332-602 info@mkosinergijaplus.org www.mkosinergijaplus.org	Željko Bogdanić
10	SUNRISE Envera Šehovića 16A 71 000 Sarajevo	033/ 278-020; 278-032 sunrise@B&H.net sunrise@microsunrise.ba http://www.microsunrise.ba	Mirsad Milavić
11	ŽENE ZA ŽENE International Dzemala Bijedića 130 71 000 Sarajevo	033/ 469-970; 469-971; 451-341 zene@B&H.net http://www.womenforwomen.org/	Seida Sarić
12	LIDER Kundurđiluk 3 71 000 Sarajevo	033/475-395; 233-180 zijadh@lider.ba http://www.lider.ba	Zijad Hasović

